

Genotypic response to aluminum toxicity of some rice

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One of the major soil constraints to rice production in tropical soils is acidity-related aluminum (Al) toxicity. The traditional method of liming is economically viable and sustainable only when lime is available locally. The alternative is to identify adaptable rice genotypes. The widely grown rice landraces are *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima*.

Fifteen *O. sativa* and 15 *O. glaberrima* genotypes were initially screened for tolerance for Al toxicity. Pregerminated seeds (5 d) were grown for 28 d in nutrient solution under three levels of Al concentration (0, 0.4, and 1.2 mM as $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) using a modified IRRRI nutrient solution for rice. These genotypes were grown in separate containers, arranged in a completely randomized design, and replicated thrice. The solution was maintained at $\text{pH } 4.2 \pm 1$ and was continuously aerated. At harvest, dry shoot and root weights were recorded after measuring shoot and root lengths.

Four selected *O. glaberrima* genotypes [a white-grain *O. glaberrima* mutant—SMMG 88-9, its parent Gorbai, Seniwa, and WAC102531(2)], two *O. sativa* genotypes (IDSA6 and Ngbongo nyenye), and the Al-tolerant check (E425) were grown at five Al concentrations (0, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, and 3.2 mM) for 28 d. The design was a split plot with levels of Al as main plots and varieties as subplots, replicated four times. The concentration of Al in duplicate

samples of the shoot was determined by the irradiation neutron activation analysis (INAA) method.

Response to Al varied widely within but not between rice species (see table). The increase in most growth measurements at low Al concentration (0.4 mM) suggests the need for some amount of Al for rice growth. Regardless of species or variety, increasing the Al concentration decreased shoot weight (Fig. 1a). The relative reduction in growth measurements caused by high Al concentration at 1.6 and 3.2 mM was 44–71% for shoot weight, 53–58% for root weight, 28–53% for shoot length, and 54–85% for root length. Thus, root length, followed by shoot weight, is most sensitive to Al toxicity.

At 1.6 and 3.2 mM Al, genotypic differences based on growth measurements were consistent, giving the following order of tol-

erance for Al toxicity: Ngbongo nyenye > WAC102531(2) > E 425 (check) = Gorbai (P) > Seniwa = IDSA6 = SMMG 88-9. Thus, the local *O. sativa* Ngbongo nyenye and *O. glaberrima* WAC102531(2) are the most tolerant, whereas elite *O. sativa* IDSA6 and mutant SMMG 88-9 were the most susceptible. Al uptake was higher in tolerant genotypes [WAC102531(2) and E 425] than in susceptible genotypes (IDSA6, SMMG 88-9, and Seniwa) (Fig. 1B). This suggests that the mechanism of tolerance in WAC102531(2) and E425 may be related to their ability to tolerate high Al in the tissue, presumably by Al detoxification. Conversely, for the Al-tolerant genotype Ngbongo nyenye, the lowest shoot Al concentration may suggest a tolerance mechanism of Al exclusion in the root apoplasm.

Growth measurements of *Oryza sativa* and *O. glaberrima* grown at different Al concentrations.*

Measurement	Al concentration (mM)					
	0		0.4		1.3	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
<i>O. sativa</i>						
Shoot weight (g)	0.54–0.96	0.74 b	0.59–1.22	0.87 a	0.27–0.57	0.36 c
Root weight (g)	0.16–0.29	0.23 b	0.15–0.34	0.25 a	0.09–0.21	0.13 c
Shoot length (cm)	27–38	31 a	25–37	31 a	17–34	20 b
Root length (cm)	16–26	21 b	18–27	23 b	7–13	10 c
Relative growth rate	3.9–5.9	4.9 b	4.5–6.6	5.4 a	2.7–4.1	3.5 c
<i>O. glaberrima</i>						
Shoot weight (g)	0.51–1.05	0.75 b	0.60–1.13	0.88 a	0.28–0.53	0.39 c
Root weight (g)	0.19–0.40	0.27 b	0.22–0.41	0.30 a	0.09–0.20	0.15 c
Shoot length (cm)	23–35	27 b	19–31	26 a	9–15	12 c
Root length (cm)	19–26	23 b	19–31	26 a	9–15	12 c
Relative growth rate	* 3.8–5.7	4.7 b	4.5–6.3	5.3 b	2.8–4.8	3.4 c

*Values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.